

LOWERING THE COST FOR COMPOSITES USED AS SECONDARY AIRCRAFT STRUCTURE

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SUMMARY: This paper looks at alternative methods that reduce the cost of fabricating composite panels used on secondary aircraft structure for propulsion systems of commercial airplanes. Since today's method of producing composite panels contribute 40 percent of the total cost of a propulsion package (less the engines), a method is needed that can further reduce cost by 50 percent without increasing weight.

Keywords: low cost, aircraft, structure

The cost drivers as shown in Table 1. and found to be:

- 1) Raw material
- 2) Labor hours
- 3) Consumables
- 4) Tooling

- 5) Cost of capital equipment used
- 6) Other (including floor space, energy usage, engineering support)

Table 1: Cost Driver associated with fabricating

composite panels for secondary aircraft structure for propulsion systems of commercial aircraft.

With raw materials contributing more than 40 percent of the total, it will be difficult to reduce the total by 50 percent without first tackling this, the largest cost driver. This can be done by moving further down the value chain; using material closer to the raw stage. Significant savings is also accomplished by reducing the amount of touch labor, with further smaller savings in tooling and capital equipment costs.

Pre-preg hand lay-up with honeycomb core was the base-line method. The following six build methods were our alternatives that we evaluated against the base-line:

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| <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Auto fiber placement with slit tape 2) Resin film infusion with core 3) Liquid resin infusion (sealed core) | <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4) Resin infusion with (K-Cor®) 5) Resin film infusion with hat stiffeners 6) Short fibers infused over foam core |
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Previous experience revealed these methods had the best chance of reducing one or more of the major cost drivers.

There are a number of other build methods, that while having the potential to reduce costs further, are still in the experimental stage. These include non-thermo curing, alternative compaction and the use of blended fibers.

Six different tooling materials and build processes were screened for tooling costs impact:

- 1) Machined invar
- 2) Formed thin sheet invar
- 3) Hand laid-up high temperature composite
- 4) Resin infused high-temperature composite
- 5) Self heated ceramic
- 6) Ceramic

Table 2 shows the relative tooling cost per part using the different methods after all adjustments.

Master patterns are required for all these methods except machined invar, adding from \$2000 to \$20,000 per square meter. This cost is only applied to the first tool. Tool life is dependent on the tool process, requiring accounting for replacement tools.

In arriving to the total tooling costs, we included; initial tool design and build cost, cost of any masters, cost of rate tools needed, expected tool life (and cost of replacing), and tool maintenance cost.

Table 2: Relative tooling cost per part.

Cost Estimating Ground Rules

Total costs were based on a common nacelle fan cowl door of 9.3² meter (100² feet). A rate of two parts every three working days was used with a total requirement of 6000 units.

Capital equipment costs were adjusted on a cost per hour basis. The cost was based on a utilization rate of 85 percent of the total available hours in the year. A useful life of 30 years was used for autoclaves and ovens, and 10 years for all other equipment. A salvage value of 15 percent was applied. Ten percent of the purchase price was added for maintenance each year. Significant cost impact would occur if the equipment were not utilized for other production parts.

Overhead bias was removed using a flat \$100 per hour labor rate.

Raw material costs are based on multi-year buys that were combined with other parts to secure the lowest prices.

The build matrix included all the options. The cost of material and rent for the capital equipment was applied. Finally, we established the final ranking after a price adjustment at a rate of \$550 per kilogram for weight loss or gain from the base line.

The results show that there is a very large cost difference pending the build method and materials used. In addition, the research points out where additional work needs to be done to further reduce costs.

I) Methods Evaluated

Baseline (pre-preg hand lay-up with honeycomb core)

- 1) Materials
 - (a) Form
 - (i) Pre-impregnated carbon fabric
 - (ii) Nomex honeycomb
 - (iii) Lighting strike mesh
 - (iv) Glass pre-preg
 - (v) Adhesive film
 - (vi) Foaming adhesive
- 2) Labor steps
 - (a) Clean and apply release to lay-up mold
 - (b) Cut and kit plies
 - (c) Lay down adhesive film, lighting strike mesh and isolation ply of glass pre-preg.
 - (d) Bag and compact plies
 - (e) Lay down outer mold line (OML) plies of pre-preg
 - (f) Bag and compact plies
 - (g) Lay down layer of film adhesive
 - (h) Lay down honeycomb core
 - (i) Splice core with foaming adhesive
 - (j) Hand work core splices
 - (k) Bag and compact core
 - (l) Lay down layer of film adhesive
 - (m) Lay down over-core plies
 - (n) Bag and compact plies
 - (o) Bag for autoclave (with breather)
 - (p) Inspect bag for leaks
 - (q) Autoclave cure
 - (r) De-mold
 - (s) Trim profile and cutouts
 - (t) Deburr
 - (u) Install inserts
 - (v) Paint
 - (w) Cure paint
 - (x) Inspect and ship

- 3) Tooling required
 - (a) Lay-up mold
 - (b) Trim fixture
- 4) Consumables required
 - (a) Bagging
 - (b) Breather
 - (c) Mold release
- 5) Capital equipment required
 - (a) Autoclave
 - (b) Laser ply template
 - (c) N/C mill or water jet for trim

Alternate methods evaluated

A) Auto fiber placed slit tapes

- 1) Materials
 - (a) Form
 - (i) Pre-impregnated carbon fabric slit to tape
 - (ii) Nomex honeycomb
 - (iii) Lighting strike mesh
 - (iv) Glass pre-preg
 - (v) Adhesive film
 - (vi) Foaming Adhesive
- 2) Labor steps.
 - (a) Clean and apply release to lay-up mold
 - (b) Lay down adhesive film, lighting strike mesh and isolation ply of glass pre-preg
 - (c) Bag and compact plies
 - (d) Lay down under core plies of pre-preg tape
 - (e) Lay down layer of film adhesive
 - (f) Lay down honeycomb core
 - (g) Splice core with foaming adhesive
 - (h) Hand work core splices

- (i) Bag and compact core
- (j) Lay down layer of film adhesive
- (k) Lay down over-core plies
- (l) Bag and compact plies
- (m) Bag for autoclave (with breather)
- (n) Inspect bag for leaks
- (o) Autoclave cure
- (p) De-mold
- (q) Trim profile and cutouts
- (r) Deburr
- (s) Install inserts
- (t) Paint
- (u) Cure paint
- (v) Inspect and ship

3) Tooling required

- (a) Lay-up mold
- (b) Trim fixture

4) Consumables required

- (a) Bagging
- (b) Breather
- (c) Mold release

5) Capital Equipment required

- (a) Autoclave
- (b) Fiber Placement Machine
- (c) N/C mill or water jet for trim

B) Resin film infusion with core

1) Materials

- (a) Form
 - (i) Dry non-crimped woven carbon fabric pre-forms.
 - (ii) Tri-axial braided edge band.
 - (iii) Nomex honeycomb
 - (iv) Resin film.
 - (v) PPK Film

2) Labor steps

- (a) Clean and apply release to lay-up mold

- (b) Run pre-forms thru semi-pregger
- (c) Cut and kit plies
- (d) Lay down under core pre-forms
- (e) Bag and compact plies
- (f) Lay down Honeycomb core with edge band
- (g) Splice core with foaming adhesive
- (h) Hand work core splices
- (i) Bag and compact core
- (j) Lay down over core plies
- (k) Bag and compact plies
- (l) Bag for cure (with breather)
- (m) Inspect bag for leaks
- (n) Cure (self heated lay-up mold)
- (o) De-mold
- (p) Post cure
- (q) Trim profile and cutouts
- (r) Deburr
- (s) Install inserts
- (t) Paint
- (u) Cure paint
- (v) Inspect and ship

3) Tooling required

- (a) Self heated lay-up mold
- (b) Trim fixture

4) Consumables required

- (a) Bagging
- (b) Breather
- (c) Mold release

5) Capital Equipment required

- (a) Semi-pregger
- (b) Post curing oven.

C) Liquid Resin Infusion (sealed core)

1) Materials

- (a) Form
 - (i) Dry non-crimped woven carbon fabric pre-forms

- (ii) Tri-axial braided edge band
- (iii) Nomex honeycomb
- (iv) Liquid Resin
- (v) PPK film

2) Labor steps

- (a) Clean and apply release to lay-up mold
- (b) Lay down PPK film on core lay-up mold
- (c) Assemble core on core lay-up mold
- (d) Splice core with foaming adhesive
- (e) Hand work core splices
- (f) Lay down PPK film on top of core
- (g) Bag core
- (h) Check bag for leaks
- (i) Cure core
- (j) Debag core
- (k) Trim core and machine required ramps
- (l) Seal core edges and ramps as required
- (m) Run pre-forms thru semi-pregger
- (n) Cut and kit plies
- (o) Lay down under core pre-forms
- (p) Bag and compact plies
- (q) Lay down core with edge band
- (r) Lay down over core plies
- (s) Bag and compact plies
- (t) Bag for cure (with breather)
- (u) Inspect bag for leaks
- (v) Inject resin
- (w) Cure (self heated lay-up mold)
- (x) De-mold
- (y) Post cure
- (z) Trim profile and cutouts
- (aa) Deburr
- (bb) Install inserts
- (cc) Paint
- (dd) Cure paint
- (ee) Inspect and ship

3) Tooling required.

- (a) Core lay-up mold
- (b) Vacuum fixture for core trim

- (c) Lay-up mold (self heated)
- (d) Trim fixture

4) Consumables required

- (a) Bagging
- (b) Breather
- (c) Mold release

5) Capital Equipment required

- (a) N/C core trim machine
- (b) Post curing oven
- (c) N/C mill or water jet for trim

D) Resin Infusion (K-Cor®)

1) Materials

- (a) Form
 - (i) Dry non-crimped woven carbon fabric pre-forms
 - (ii) Tri-axial braided edge band
 - (iii) Foam core
 - (iv) Liquid resin

2) Labor steps.

- (a) Insert pins in foam
- (b) Trim foam
- (c) Form foam core
- (d) Clean and apply release to lay-up mold
- (e) Lay down under core pre-forms
- (f) Bag and compact plies
- (g) Lay down core with edge band
- (h) Lay down over core plies
- (i) Bag and compact plies
- (j) Bag for cure with breather
- (k) Inspect bag for leaks
- (l) Inject resin
- (m) Cure (self heated lay-up mold)
- (n) De-mold
- (o) Post cure
- (p) Trim profile and cutouts
- (q) Deburr
- (r) Install inserts
- (s) Paint

- (t) Cure paint
- (u) Inspect and ship

3) Tooling required

- (a) Core forming mandrel
- (b) Lay-up mold (self heated)
- (c) Trim fixture

4) Consumables required

- (a) Bagging
- (b) Breather
- (c) Mold release

5) Capital equipment required

- (a) Pin inserting machine
- (b) Post curing oven
- (c) N/C mill or water jet for trim

E) Resin Film Infusion with Hat Stiffeners

1) Materials

- (a) Form
 - (i) Dry non-crimped woven carbon fabric pre-forms
 - (ii) Tri-axial braided edge band
 - (iii) Tri-axial braided stiffeners
 - (iv) Resin film

2) Labor steps

- (a) Clean and apply release to lay-up mold
- (b) Lay down face sheet pre-forms
- (c) Bag and compact plies
- (d) Lay-up stiffeners with resin film
- (e) Install stiffener supports
- (f) Bag and compact stiffeners
- (g) Bag for cure with breather
- (h) Inspect bag for leaks
- (i) Autoclave cure
- (j) De-mold
- (k) Trim profile and cutouts
- (l) Deburr
- (m) Install inserts

- (n) Paint
- (o) Cure paint
- (p) Inspect and ship

3) Tooling required

- (a) Lay-up mold (self heated)
- (b) Stiffener mandrels
- (c) Trim fixture

4) Consumables required

- (a) Bagging
- (b) Breather
- (c) Mold release

5) Capital Equipment required

- (a) Autoclave
- (b) N/C mill or water jet for trim

F) Short fiber with Foam Core

1) Materials

- (a) Form
 - (i) Graphite roving
 - (ii) Lighting strike mesh
 - (iii) Glass pre-preg
 - (iv) Foam core (K-Core®)
 - (v) Liquid resin

2) Labor steps

- (a) Chop fiber and spray preforms
- (b) Remove and rough trim preforms
- (c) Insert pins in foam
- (d) Trim foam
- (e) Form foam core
- (f) Clean and apply release to lay-up mold
- (g) Lay down adhesive film, lighting strike mesh, and isolation ply of glass pre-preg
- (h) Bag and compact plies
- (i) Lay down under core pre-form
- (j) Bag and compact pre-form
- (k) Lay down core

- (l) Lay down over core pre-form
- (m) Bag and compact pre-form
- (n) Bag for cure with breather
- (o) Inspect bag for leaks
- (p) Inject resin
- (q) Cure (self heated lay-up mold)
- (r) De-mold
- (s) Post cure
- (t) Trim profile and cutouts
- (u) Deburr
- (v) Install inserts
- (w) Paint
- (x) Cure paint
- (y) Inspect and ship

3) Tooling required

- (a) Core forming mandrel
- (b) Lay-up mold (self heated)
- (c) Pre-form spray wire Forms
- (d) Trim fixture

4) Consumables required

- (a) Bagging
- (b) Breather
- (c) Mold release

5) Capital Equipment required

- (a) Post curing oven
- (b) Pin inserting machine
- (c) Chopper sprayer
- (d) N/C mill or water jet for trim

II) Results

Base Line = Pre-preg hand lay-up with honey-comb core

Case A = Auto Fiber Placement with slit tape

Case B = Resin Film Infusion with core

Case C = Liquid Resin Infusion (sealed core)

Case D = Resin Infusion with (K-Cor®)

Case E = Resin Film Infusion with hat stiffeners

Case F = Short Fibers infused over foam core

The high and low values show are do to the degree of uncertainty in the data.

Table A: The material costs reflect the total cost of the raw materials, including waste to make a complete part. Waste can be a significant factor in material costs using different lay up methods.

Table B: The labor hours include all touch labor required to fabricate the part. The time that a part spends in an autoclave or oven is assumed to be multi-tasking and is charged at one-eighth of the labor time. It also does not include any queue or wait time between operations. The rollup cost was computed using a nominal direct labor rate of \$100 per hour, to allow for overhead charges.

Table C: The flow hours show the total hours that it takes to complete the process including set up and run times. No allowance has been added for any wait or queue time between operations.

Table D: This chart shows the tooling cost spread out over a possible total run of 6,000 parts with a 10 percent of the purchase price allowance for tool maintenance per year added in. It also allows for rate tools if the process requires them to maintain a production rate of 14 parts per month and any replacement tools needed.

Table E: Capital equipment cost was computed based on the hours of use of each asset. The equipment is assumed to have a useful life of 10 years for machine tools and 30 years for autoclaves and ovens. There is 10 percent maintenance per year added to the machine tools and 5 percent to ovens and autoclaves. There is a significant impact if the equipment is not fully utilized on other parts.

Table F: These costs are for the non-flying materials needed to manufacture. The autoclaves also have a \$500.00 per use charge for nitrogen.

Table G: Weights shown are the finished weight of the composite panel only and do not allow for fittings or inserts.

Table H: Presented is a rollup of both the recurring and non-recurring costs on a per part basis.

Table I: The total cost to the airplane after including an allowance of \$550 per kilogram. Total weight is a big factor we have to consider and the one that has the most potential for improvement.

III) Notes

The non-crimped woven preforms incorporate the lighting strike protection woven into the OML performs.

The baseline and Cases A and E used Invar tools and an autoclave cure; all others used self-heated ceramic with an oven post cure.

No effort was made to improve the cost associated with the finishing processes, (i.e. non-destructive inspection, painting, final trimming and insert and fitting installation.) This is another area that, although only a small percentage of the total, has much room for improvement.

IV) Discussion

As Table A shows, compared to the pre-preg & honeycomb raw materials, Cases B, C cost approximately 70-75% less while Cases D & F cost approximately 70-80% less than the baseline materials. Cases A & E material costs were 30-55% less than the baseline material.

Table B shows recurring costs associated with each process. Compared to the hand lay-up pre-preg process, Cases A, B, C & E required approximately 50% less touch labor to fabricate the 100 ft² nacelle fan cowl door. Evaluating Cases D & F processes showed further recurring labor costs reduction of as much as 75% the baseline costs.

Table C shows Flow Time of each process. Again, Cases D and F showed the most reduction, with approximately 50% less manufacturing flow time compared to the baseline. The balance Cases showed only 20-35% less time than the pre-preg baseline. By stopping the evaluation of these cases after looking at only material costs, recurring labor and flow time, we would erroneously show Case D (Resin Infusion with (K-Cor®)) or Case F (Short Fibers infused over foam core) as the best alternatives to hand laying-up pre-preg.

Table D shows the Tooling Costs to fabricate the fan cowl door. The surprise is Case E (Resin Film Infusion with hat stiffeners) at 50% more costs than the hand lay up pre-preg baseline process. This is because hollow hat section tooling has limited life and requires regular replacing. Here, Cases B, C, D, & F all hover at approximately 60% less tooling cost than hand lay-up tools. Depending upon the Case A (Auto Fiber Placement with slit tape) tooling used, savings of 30-60% can be seen.

Table E shows the manufacturing process Capital Costs. Case A (Auto Fiber Placement with slit tape) capital can cost as much as 100% more than hand lay-up pre-preg capital. Here again, Case D (Resin Infusion with (K-Cor®)) or Case F (Short Fibers infused over foam core) were the best alternatives by showing reductions in capital costs as much as 75% to hand laying-up pre-preg. Case E (Resin Film Infusion with hat stiffeners) showed as much as 60% less capital costs.

Table F shows the manufacturing process Consumable Costs. The best processes savings were with Cases D, E & F with 35 – 60%. There is an opportunity to reduce these costs with an improved reusable bagging method, or using a different type of compaction.

Table G shows the Weight comparisons of all of the materials and their respective manufacturing processes. Cases D & E show the most savings at 20- 25% from the hand laid process and Case F. Weight is partially attributed to matching

physical properties between the Cases and at the current level of composite maturity, these fan cowl door weights were within 20% of one another.

Table H shows the combined Non-Recurring and Recurring of each Case. Case D (Resin Infusion with (K-Cor®)) or Case F (Short Fibers infused over foam core) had as much as 65-75 % reduced total costs over the baseline process.

Table I shows the influence of weight on the process. Even at a very modest charge of \$550 per kilogram, this makes a very large difference in the outcome of the trade.

V) Conclusions

The data shows that it is possible to reduce the costs.

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It is readily apparent that this is a complex problem that needs more work.

Looking into different forms of material, methods of lay down and better methods of curing is the place to start.

New resin systems and fiber forms need to be developed that will allow provide the needed properties using alternate lay down methods and curing that can further reduce costs.

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